

SHORT NOTES

VOLUMETRIC METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF SMALL AMOUNTS OF SILVER IN PRESENCE OF LARGE AMOUNTS OF COPPER AND NICKEL

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The titration of silver by Volhard's method has some limitations if copper also is present. Determination of silver in ores and alloys by starch-iodine method (Pisani, *Ann. Min.*, 1856, 83; Field, *Chem. News*, 1860, 2, 17) is not satisfactory when the percentage of copper is very high as it would be difficult to weaken the colour of the copper and nickel even by large dilution.

In the present work the reaction of silver ion with iodine in potassium iodide solution has been studied under different p_H and it has been found that the determination of silver by titrating with iodine-iodide solution, using starch as an internal indicator, can be done in the presence of an excess of sodium acetate or sodium bicarbonate. In sodium acetate buffer medium, the end-point is more sharp. Hence, this medium has been chosen for the present determination. Here, both iodine and iodide enter into the reaction whereas in ordinary iodimetry, the concentration of iodine alone counts. Hence, iodine-iodide solution is standardised against a known silver nitrate solution. The presence of copper and nickel will not interfere with the estimation.

Silver salts react with iodine with the formation of unstable hypoiodous acid which is more stable in neutral or acidic medium :

But in sodium acetate buffer medium, the decomposition of hypoiodous acid to iodic acid is practically complete and the regenerated HI further reacts with the silver salts :

This reaction can be substantiated by determining the amount of KI and free iodine present per c.c. of iodine-iodide solution. The reaction of silver salts with KI is simple :

Procedure.—Pure KI (10.0 g.) was dissolved in distilled water (15-20 c.c.) ; pure iodine (A.R., 6.3 g.) was carefully introduced into the KI solution and stirred in the

cold till the iodine completely dissolved. Immediately, the solution was transferred to a glass-stoppered 2-litre flask and the volume made up to the mark with distilled water.

To a neutral $N/50$ - AgNO_3 solution (10 or 20 c.c.), taken in a 250 c.c. conical flask, a 20% sodium acetate (extra pure) solution (25 c.c.) was added and diluted to 100 c.c. with distilled water. A freshly prepared 1% starch solution (2-3 c.c.) was added and then it was titrated slowly with iodine-iodide solution from a burette to the first definite starch-iodine end-point. A blank test was carried out taking 100 c.c. of distilled water containing 5.0 g. of sodium acetate. The volume of iodine-iodide solution required in the blank titration was deducted from the volume required in the original titration. The silver value of 1 c.c. of iodine-iodide solution was thus determined. It is important to carry out this standardisation for each set of experiments.

Determination of Silver.—The material (2.5 g.) was dissolved in HNO_3 (d 1.2) and then fumed with 10 c.c. of H_2SO_4 (conc.) cautiously over a sand-bath. Most of the acid was removed by fuming. The residue was dissolved in distilled water and transferred to a 250 c.c. measuring flask, filtering, if necessary, and the volume was made up to the mark. An aliquot volume of the solution was taken in a 250 c.c. flask, neutralised by NaHCO_3 solution (conc.), added dropwise from a burette, and then titrated as usual with the standard iodine-iodide solution, after adding sodium acetate. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	% Cu in mixture.	% Ni in mixture.	Ag (calc.).	Ag (found).	% Error.
1.	99.20	Nil	0.00405 g.	0.00403 g.	0.49
2.	99.93	Nil	0.00540	0.00542	0.37
3.	97.89	Nil	0.01080	0.01091	1.01
4.	95.76	Nil	0.02214	0.02236	0.99
5.	92.05	Nil	0.02160	0.02147	0.60
6.	88.52	Nil	0.03240	0.03266	0.80
7.	85.26	Nil	0.04320	0.04298	0.51
8.	82.23	Nil	0.05400	0.05400	0.00
9.	54.25	43.40	0.01080	0.01089	0.83
10.	52.31	43.24	0.02160	0.02151	0.41
11.	63.58	24.43	0.04320	0.04316	0.09
12.	43.10	45.26	0.05400	0.05378	0.41

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